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ASSOCIATION OF ANISOTROPIC LIPOPHILICITY OF 1-ARYL-3-METHYLSUCCINIMIDES OBTAINED BY RP-HPLC WITH IN SILICO PERMEABILITY PREDICTORS

Nataša Milošević¹, Nemanja Todorović¹, Mladena Lalić-Popović¹, Dunja Vidović¹, Jelena Čanji Panić¹, Nebojša Banjac²

¹*University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Hajduk Veljkova 3, 21000 Novi Sad, natasa.milosevic@mf.uns.ac.rs*

²*University of Belgrade, Faculty of Agriculture, Food Technology and Biochemistry, Nemanjina 6, 11080, Belgrade, Zemun, Serbia*

Introduction: Certain properties of the whole molecule represent important molecular descriptors in the modeling of complex pharmacokinetic properties. Lipophilicity is a physico-chemical characteristic of a compound that directly affects the biological activity of a chemical entity. **Material and methods:** Thirteen newly synthesized 1-aryl-3-methylsuccinimides were analysed by reverse phase high performance liquid chromatography (RP-HPLC) for determining their lipophilicity. Chromatographic measurements were conducted on Agilent 1100 apparatus, with DAD detector and binary pump on C18 column (Hypersil ODS, 100mm×2.1; 5 μm). Binary mixture of water and methanol (HPLC grade, JTBaker) with the volume ratio varied from 45:55 to 65:35 was used as the mobile phase. The flow of the mobile phase was 0.8 ml/min with constant temperature at 25 °C. The compounds were detected on λ=205 nm. The online tool pkCSM was applied for determining Caco-2 permeability, logPapp (10⁻⁶ cm/s), intestinal absorption, IA (%), logarithm of blood-brain permeability, logBBB and logarithm of skin permeability, logKp for all analyzed compounds. **Results:** Anisotropic lipophilicity expressed as logKw was determined for twelve compounds based on the retention times obtained by RP-HPLC with the variation of the mobile phase. The compound with carboxylic group was completely ionised and thus was eluted with the mobile phase as pre-pick. The association of the logKw values with logPapp (r²=0.381, p=0.019), logBBB (r²=0.488, p=0.007) and logKp (r²=0.536, p=0.004) respectively were linear suggesting that the increment of lipophilicity of the observed compounds was followed by the enhanced permeability through the lipophilic obstacles such as the intestinal membranes, the blood-brain barrier and the skin. The correlation between logKw and the IA was described with a parabolic function in a statistically significant manner (r²=0.439, p=0.030). **Conclusion:** Anisotropic lipophilicity of the analyzed 1-aryl-3-methylsuccinimides reflects their predicted permeability through different physiological barriers.

Keywords: Lipophilicity, Permeability, Chromatography

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